

Tracking Graduates' Outcomes in a State University

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Abstract:

This descriptive quantitative research determined to track the outcomes of the graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management of the State University of Northern Negros in terms of their employment status, work or job position, and salary grade before and after their graduation. Likewise, determined the extent of outcomes as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors in the areas of professional development, research capabilities, innovativeness, leadership capabilities, management spheres, and communication capabilities. This study used ANOVA and t-test in establishing that a significant difference exists in the extent of outcomes between and among the results of the survey. Findings was a highly significant difference in the area of the professional development ($p=0.003$) and a significant difference in the area of the research capabilities ($p=0.036$) of the PhD-EM graduates. The pattern and strength of the finding suggests that there was a very great extent in the outcomes in their research quality ($\bar{x}=4.34$), innovativeness ($\bar{x}=4.33$), leadership capabilities ($\bar{x}=4.33$), management spheres ($\bar{x}=4.42$), and communication capabilities ($\bar{x}=4.36$). Thus, it serves to broaden competencies in cultivating an equitable and sustainable higher education landscape that could produce locally responsive, innovative, and globally competitive graduates so that sustainable development will be attained with graduates can spur and sustain the skills. Also, graduates of PhD-EM must widen their perspectives or horizon by revisiting their purpose of achieving the degree through understanding the depth of acquiring the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management and apply their acquired skills and knowledge in their respective organizations.

Keywords: Doctorate Program, Management, State University, Professional Development, Research Capabilities

Introduction:

In the Philippines, graduate education is vital in any organization as it plays an important role in the development of manpower that can provide leadership to efforts geared toward national development. It molds the human resources needed to propel at least two important driving forces of development – education and research.

According to Tutor et al. (2021), to understand how well SUNN has performed in terms of developing the competencies of its students and to gather information about the employability and employment status of its graduates, as well as their feedback on the degree program, there is a need to conduct a graduate tracer study. It could be an approach to track and keep a record of its students. Graduate tracer studies are one form of empirical research that can appropriately provide valuable information for evaluating the results of the education and training of a specific institution of higher education to be used as material for continuous improvement and quality assurance of the educational institutions.

SUNN PhD-EM program, according to Senining (2020), should develop the management skills of its students and may not be limited to certain major fields confined to office or school supervision but also to the areas that demand industrial expertise. Also, the research capabilities of PhD-EM students must be developed as it is a need when they are already in their respective fields of work.

Hence, this study determined the PhD-EM graduates of the SUNN had gone. Also, this explanatory sequential inquiry will determine the contribution of SUNN to the satisfaction with the delivery of the graduate school program and services, and the practice of graduate attributes of the program from 2020-2023. Likewise, it explored deeper insights to the quantitative data to generate a broader perspective on the graduates' experiences on its contributions to the development of their skills, satisfaction with the delivery of programs and services, and graduate attribute practice.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to track the outcomes of the graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program of the State University of Northern Negros from the School year 2020-2023. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: (a) what is the profile of the graduates of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program of 2020-2023 in terms of age, sex, and year graduated? (b) what is the employment data of the graduates of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program in terms of employment status before and after graduation, work/job position before and after graduation, and salary grade before and after graduation? (c) what is the extent of outcomes among the PhD-EM graduates as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors in the areas of professional development, research capabilities, innovativeness, leadership capabilities,

management spheres, and communication capabilities? (d) is there a significant difference in the extent of graduates' outcomes based on the aforementioned areas as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors? (e) based on the findings of the study, what intervention schemes can be employed to further prepare the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management students after graduation?

Methodology

This section discusses the research design use, the locale of the study, the respondents of the study, the sampling technique, the research instrument, the validity and reliability of the instrument, the data gathering procedure, and the statistical procedures use in the analysis of data.

Research Design

This study used a descriptive quantitative research design to track graduate students of a state university. According to Creswell & Creswell (2018), this approach allows for the collection of measurable numerical data for statistical analysis. Descriptive research, as noted by Hubbard (2016), focuses on gathering data to describe a phenomenon, which may or may not be quantifiable. The study aimed to assess current conditions and examine relationships among variables, making the descriptive quantitative design appropriate. Data from SUNN's PhD in Educational Management graduates (2019–2023) were used to describe their profiles and employment status, providing a reliable basis for conclusions.

Participants of the Study

The respondents of the study were the forty-two (42) graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management of State University of Northern Negros from School Year 2020 to 2023.

Table 1. Respondents of the Study

Academic Year	N	%
2020-2021	11	26.19%
2021-2022	17	40.48%
2022-2023	14	33.33%
Total	42	100.00%

Research Instrument

This study adapted the instrument of Senining (2020) to evaluate the extent of graduates' outcomes. The tool had four parts: (1) general respondent information; (2) profile data by age, sex, and year graduated; (3) employment details before and after graduation, including job status, position, and salary; and (4) assessment of graduate outcomes by both the graduates and their immediate supervisors in areas such as professional development, research, innovation, leadership, management, and communication. Responses were rated using a Likert scale.

Data Gathering Procedure

After confirming the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher administered the questionnaire using Google Forms to reach respondents both locally and internationally. Invitations were sent via Facebook Messenger, Yahoo Mail, Gmail, and Microsoft Outlook, accompanied by an explanation of the study's purpose. Printed copies were also distributed to participants who preferred face-to-face administration. A letter of assurance regarding data privacy and confidentiality was included. All responses were encoded, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis, aligned with the research objectives.

Data Analysis Procedure

The analytical schemes employed by the researcher based on the research objectives of this study were distribution, descriptive, and comparative. In the analyses of the data, the following statistical tools were used.

For the first objective in determining the profile of the graduates of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program of 2020-2023 in terms of age, sex, and the year they graduated, frequency and percentage were used.

For the second objective in determining the employment data of the graduates of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program in terms of employment status, work/job position, and salary grade, frequency and percentage were used.

The third objective which determined the extent of outcomes among the PhD-EM graduates as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors in the areas of professional development, research capabilities, innovativeness, leadership capabilities, management spheres, and communication capabilities, mean and standard deviation were used.

For the fourth objective which determined which sought to find out if there exist a significant difference in the extent of graduates' outcomes as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors, ANOVA and t-test were used.

The mean scores for the extent of outcomes among the PhD-EM graduates as assessed by themselves and by their immediate supervisors were interpreted with the use of the following indicator:

Weight	Mean Score Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.21 – 5.00	Very Great Extent
4	3.41 – 4.20	Great Extent
3	2.61 – 3.40	Moderate Extent
2	1.81 – 2.60	Low Extent
1	1.00 – 1.80	Very Low Extent

Ethical Consideration

Ethical standards were observed throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained during data collection, and all records were kept confidential. Participant privacy was ensured, with data accessible only to the researcher and, if published, presented in aggregate form to protect individual identities.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the data collected were organized in tabular forms. The researcher's analysis and interpretation of the data are presented as well as the implications of the result of this study.

Table 2 below presents the distribution of respondents by age, sex, and year of graduation. Among the 42 respondents, the majority (57.1%) are aged 31–40, followed by 40.5% aged 41 and above, and only 2.4% aged 21–30. Most respondents are female (76.2%), while 23.8% are male. In terms of graduation year, 40.5% graduated in 2021–2022, 33.3% in 2022–2023, and 26.2% in 2020–2021.

These findings suggest that most PhD in Educational Management graduates are women aged 31–40. This supports Bahl's (2024) view that older graduate students often return to study with greater focus and experience, though they may face challenges balancing study with work or personal commitments. The higher number of female PhD graduates also aligns with Perry (2021), who attributes this trend to increasing educational access, gender equity initiatives, and growing female representation in fields like education and the social sciences.

Table 2. Distributions of Respondents Based on Selected Variables

Variables	(f)	(%)
Age		
21-30	1	2.4
31-40	24	57.1
41 and above	17	40.5
Total	42	100.0
Sex		
Male	10	23.8
Female	32	76.2
Total	42	100.0
Year Graduated		
2020-2021	11	26.2
2021-2022	17	40.5
2022-2023	14	33.3
Total	42	100.0

Employment Data of the Graduates of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management Program Before and After their Graduation

As presented in Table 3 below, the employment status of the respondents before they graduated from the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management program, there are 40 or 95.2% who are already permanent or regular in their teaching jobs, 1 or 2.4% of the respondent is a fulltime or contractual in a non-teaching job, and 1 or 2.4% is a permanent or regular in a non-teaching job. After the respondents graduated from the program, those who are permanent or regular in their teaching jobs increased by 1 making it 41 or 97.6% thus, the 1 fulltime/contractual non-teaching respondent became permanent/regular teaching. Then, 1 or 2.4% remained permanent or regular in a non-teaching job.

Table 3. Employment Status of Graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management

Status	Before Graduation		After Graduation	
	(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)
Permanent / Regular-Teaching	40	95.2	41	97.6
Fulltime / Contractual- Non-Teaching	1	2.4	0	0
Permanent/Regular -Non-Teaching	1	2.4	1	2.4
Total	42	100.0	42	100.0

Table 4 below shows the salary grade of the respondents before and after they graduated from the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management.

Before, there are 27 or 64.3% has a salary grade of 10-11, there are 12 or 28.6% with a salary grade of 12-13, 1 or 2.4% of the respondents with a salary grade of 16-17, and 2 or 4.8% with a salary grade of 18-19. When the respondents finished their Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management, only 1 or 2.4% remained in salary grade 10-11, then 23 or 54.8% with a salary grade of 12-13, then 4 or 9.5% with a salary grade of 14-15, 1 or 2.4% with a salary grade of 16-17, 10 or 23.8% with a salary grade of 18-19, 2 or 4.8% with a salary grade of 20-21, and 1 or 2.4% with a salary grade of 22-23.

This implies that their acquisition of the Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management catapulted their salary grades as they were promoted. Before graduation, there were 27 who have salary grades of 10-11 then, after graduation only 1 left. In salary grade 12-13, after graduation there were 23 from 12 before graduation, salary grade 14-15 increased from 0 to 4, salary grade 18-19 increased to 10 from 2, salary grade 20-21 increased to 2 from 0, and salary grade 22-23 increased to 1 from 0.

Table 4. Salary Grades of Graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management

Salary Grades	Before Graduation		After Graduation	
	(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)
10-11	27	64.3	1	2.4
12-13	12	28.6	23	54.8
14-15	0	0	4	9.5
16-17	1	2.4	1	2.4

18-19	2	4.8	10	23.8
20-21	0	0	2	4.8
22-23	0	0	1	2.4
Total	42	100	42	100.0

Table 5 below presents the work positions of the respondents before and after their graduation.

The respondents before their graduation from the program, there are 38 or 90.5% who are permanent teaching staff in basic education, 1 or 2.4% is a permanent non-teaching personnel in basic education, 1 or 2.4% is a professor or associate professor in a higher education institution, and 2 or 4.8% who are in a managerial, supervisory or headship job in a higher education institution. Then, after the respondents graduated from the program, 32 or 76.2% are still in a permanent teaching position in basic education, and 10 or 23.8% holds a managerial, supervisory or headship job in a higher education institution.

This implies that after graduation, the 1 respondent who is a professor/associate professor in a higher education institution, the 1 respondent who is a permanent non-teaching personnel in basic education, and the 6 permanent teaching staff in basic education were promoted to a higher position.

Table 5. Work Position of Graduates of Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Management

Work Position	Before Graduation		After Graduation	
	(f)	(%)	(f)	(%)
Managerial/Supervisory/Headship Job in Higher Education Institution	2	4.8	10	23.8
Professor/Assoc Prof in Higher Education Institution	1	2.4	0	0
Permanent Non-Teaching Personnel in Basic Education	1	2.4	0	0
Permanent Teaching Staff in Basic Education	38	90.5	32	76.2
Total	42	100.0	42	100.0

The employment data of respondents before and after earning their PhD in Educational Management aligns with Slingo's (2023) view that professional development enhances skills, knowledge, and career advancement. It also fosters personal fulfilment and engagement in one's work. Schwartz (2023) emphasized that well-executed professional development improves teacher performance and student outcomes, while also fostering collaboration and institutional support.

Similarly, Parker (2021) noted that a PhD equips educators with specialized expertise and research skills, making them strong candidates for administrative and leadership roles. Andrews (2021) added that PhD holders benefit from greater job stability, higher salaries, and increased prestige, often qualifying for advanced instructional and policy roles. Thus, earning a PhD not only strengthens personal and professional growth but also increases opportunities for advancement in education.

Extent of Outcomes Among PhD-EM Graduates

Table 6 presents results related to the third objective—evaluating PhD-EM graduates' outcomes in professional development. The overall mean was 4.17 (SD = 0.476), indicating a great extent of outcome. The highest-rated item was "received annual training and assessment" (M = 4.40, very great extent), while the lowest was "conduct independent research" (M = 3.79, great extent).

These findings align with Cassidy (2019), who emphasized that professional development equips teachers to design relevant instruction and improve educational quality. Similarly, Kelly (2011) found that advanced education enhances transformational leadership by fostering vision and innovation. Dehgan (2020) also highlighted teachers' perceptions of professionalism as both transformative and structured. These results support the Department of Education's (DepEd, 2013) assertion that quality teaching is essential to student achievement and national development. Thus, PhD-trained teachers are better equipped to adapt, lead, and impact the profession positively.

Table 6. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Professional Development

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
1. demonstrate a presentation skill to audience effectively.	4.25	.565	Very Great Extent
2. write proposal for funding.	4.25	.617	Very Great Extent
3. conduct independent research.	3.79	.884	Great Extent
4. handle a project management.	4.11	.676	Great Extent
5. observe research professional ethics.	3.96	.684	Great Extent
6. involve in any professional organization.	4.36	.544	Very Great Extent
7. speak to non-academic audience.	4.32	.515	Very Great Extent
8. prepare articles for publication.	3.94	.758	Great Extent

9. received annual training and assessment for continuous progress.	4.40	.458	Very Great Extent
10. work in collaborative groups.	4.36	.521	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.17	.476	Great Extent

*Rating Scale: 4.20-5.0 very great; 3.40-4.19 great; 2.60-3.39 moderate; 1.80-2.59 low; 1.0-1.179 very low

Table 7 shows that the extent of research outcomes among PhD-EM graduates is rated at a very great extent, with an overall mean of 4.34 (SD = 0.415). The highest-rated outcome was the ability to formulate research-based policies and strategies (M = 4.39), while the lowest was designing experimental studies independently (M = 4.27)—both still rated at a very great extent.

These findings support Manila et al. (2022), who emphasized the role of research in improving teaching practices and educational standards. Borrell (2019) also highlighted that one key motivation for pursuing a PhD is a passion for discovery and independent inquiry, which demonstrates intellectual potential and contributes meaningfully to the academic field.

Table 7. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Research Capability

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
1. formulate research-based policies, strategies, projects that address specific problem.	4.39	.535	Very Great Extent
2. search, use, and evaluate information; be aware on various sources of information and where to obtain them.	4.33	.611	Very Great Extent
3. design experimental study independently.	4.27	.682	Very Great Extent
4. select and develop research instruments independently.	4.38	.527	Very Great Extent
5. know how to choose appropriate statistical tools.	4.32	.571	Very Great Extent
6. prepare manuscript for colloquium and for possible publication.	4.38	.515	Very Great Extent
7. facilitate regular training and guidance to different audiences.	4.36	.509	Very Great Extent
8. attend research-related training/conferences and undertake published or printed resources.	4.33	.601	Very Great Extent
9. publish scientific articles in referred journals; conference proceedings.	4.37	.574	Very Great Extent
10. execute the research process e.g. collection, analysis, interpretation, and assessment procedures.	4.29	.645	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.34	.415	Very Great Extent

Table 8 presents the extent of innovativeness among PhD-EM graduates, with an overall mean of 4.33 (SD = 0.577), indicating a very great extent. The highest-rated item was their openness to innovation proposals (M = 4.42), while the lowest was actively seeking innovative ideas (M = 4.23), both still within a very great extent.

These findings align with Süer and Karagül (2023), who emphasized that innovativeness is vital in today's fast-changing society. Tang (2021) defined it as the application of new methods in teaching and learning, a practice PhD-EM graduates appear to embrace. Xia and O'Shea (2024) noted that such practices enhance cognitive engagement, pushing beyond traditional methods. Similarly, Blömeke et al. (2021) suggested that innovative educators foster school-wide change, and Cañete (2016) stressed that innovation is nurtured through experience and further studies, developing creativity and problem-solving skills.

Table 8. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Innovativeness

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
1. welcome innovation proposals in the organization.	4.42	.535	Very Great Extent
2. seek innovation ideas actively.	4.23	.611	Very Great Extent
3. perceive innovation as too risky and is resisted.	4.27	.682	Very Great Extent
4. empower people to develop new ideas that work.	4.28	.527	Very Great Extent
5. improve traditional instructions continuously into a highly innovative teaching-learning environment.	4.32	.571	Very Great Extent
6. promote and support innovative ideas, experimentation, and creative process.	4.38	.515	Very Great Extent
7. emphasize and introduce managerial innovations (e.g. computer-based administrative innovations, new employee rewards, raining schemes, new departments or project teams, etc.)	4.37	.509	Very Great Extent
8. employ Technology-assisted work to cope up with time, effort, and money.	4.33	.601	Very Great Extent

9. train teachers and/or employee to use technology tools.	4.37	.574	Very Great Extent
10. maintain internet connection to speed up work and for research purpose.	4.29	.645	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.33	.577	Very Great Extent

Table 9 presents the extent of outcomes among PhD-EM graduates in terms of leadership capabilities, with an overall mean of 4.33 (SD= 0.408), indicating a very great extent. Leadership management scored higher (M=4.39) than leadership behavior (M = 4.28), both rated as very great. Within leadership behavior, the highest-rated item was following a clear vision and beliefs (M = 4.39), while the lowest was initiating belief-challenging changes (M = 4.02), though still rated as great. In leadership management, the top-rated item was seeking resources for programs (M = 4.44), and the lowest was sensing emotional undercurrents (M = 4.34). These results support Marques (2013), who noted that advanced studies increase the likelihood of leadership roles. Quiatchon (2020) also emphasized that doctoral graduates gain broader administrative influence and can initiate impactful change in schools. Bruens (2017) further highlighted the multifaceted responsibilities of educational administrators, noting their leadership, communication, and problem-solving skills as essential to school success.

Table 9. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Leadership Capabilities

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
Leadership Capabilities on Leadership Behavior			
1. possess advance knowledge about effective instructional practices.	4.21	.553	Very Great Extent
2. inspire teachers and employee to accomplish things that might seem beyond their grasp.	4.31	.562	Very Great Extent
3. check continually and regularly the effectiveness of the course curriculum.	4.33	.514	Very Great Extent
4. stay informed of the current research theory regarding effective schooling.	4.29	.553	Very Great Extent
5. initiate changes that require people to re-examine their beliefs and values.	4.02	.573	Great Extent
6. follow a well-defined vision and beliefs about schools, teaching, and training.	4.39	.512	Very Great Extent
7. discuss about current research in school.	4.33	.576	Very Great Extent
8. monitor closely the effectiveness of the instruction practices of teachers.	4.37	.482	Very Great Extent
9. adapt leadership style to the specific need a given situation.	4.32	.466	Very Great Extent
10. expose teachers to current ideas about how to be effective in teaching.	4.36	.509	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.28	.404	Very Great Extent
Leadership Capabilities on Leadership Management			
1. effect detailed aspect of your work.	4.38	.478	Very Great Extent
2. know ahead of time how people will respond to a new idea or proposal.	4.38	.491	Very Great Extent
3. effect solution to problems.	4.40	.445	Very Great Extent
4. ensure high trust or employee on your style of leadership.	4.37	.541	Very Great Extent
5. address problems in the organization promptly when they arise,	4.42	.467	Very Great Extent
6. manage people and resources and is considered one of your strengths.	4.40	.520	Very Great Extent
7. obtain and allocate resources efficiently and is considered a challenging aspect of your job.	4.42	.480	Very Great Extent
8. seek resources to support programs and projects.	4.44	.508	Very Great Extent
9. use emotional energy to motivate others.	4.36	.607	Very Great Extent
10. perceived usually when there is emotional undercurrent in your organization.	4.34	.568	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.39	.413	Very Great Extent
When Taken as a Whole	4.33	.408	Very Great Extent

Table 10 presents the outcomes of PhD-EM graduates in terms of three management spheres: strategy creation, human resource development, and teaching process administration. The overall mean was 4.42 (SD = 0.350), indicating outcomes to a very great extent. Teaching process administration scored highest (M = 4.44), followed by strategy creation (M = 4.43), and human resources development (M = 4.38), all rated very great.

In the strategy creation sphere, ensuring a sustainable environment was rated highest (M = 4.55), while utilizing ICT and promoting experimentation had the lowest mean (M = 4.36). In HR development, inspiring and motivating colleagues was highest (M = 4.49), and listening effectively was lowest (M = 3.86). In teaching process administration, maintaining a teachable attitude scored highest (M = 4.50), and organizing instruction around real-life problem-solving was lowest (M = 4.40).

These findings align with Bitterova et al. (2014), who highlighted the strategic role of school leaders in fostering shared values and school vision. They also support Andrews (2021), who emphasized the PhD's role in enhancing strategic thinking, analytical skills, and adaptability—traits essential for leadership in HR and education management. PhD-EM graduates demonstrate capacity for promoting a learner-centered environment, applying innovative and strategic methods to manage institutions effectively.

Table 10. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Management Sphere

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
Management Sphere on Strategy Creation Sphere			
1. elaborate school development concept; implement the common school vision.	4.42	.426	Very Great Extent
2. create motivational strategies based on shared values of the organization.	4.38	.503	Very Great Extent
3. ensure sustainable environment.	4.55	.439	Very Great Extent
4. design proactive approaches aimed at goals, processes, and results of the school.	4.46	.433	Very Great Extent
5. promote organizational culture, structure, infrastructure favorable to learning.	4.46	.473	Very Great Extent
6. know what distinguishes your organization from competitors.	4.42	.480	Very Great Extent
7. utilize information and communication technology to keep and communicate knowledge.	4.36	.544	Very Great Extent
8. encourage experimentation and exchange of ideas and values learning.	4.36	.566	Very Great Extent
9. prioritize people's job security, salary, and work life balance.	4.46	.447	Very Great Extent
10. permit innovative ideas of subordinates to flow across the entire organization.	4.45	.424	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.43	.363	Very Great Extent
Management Sphere on Managing Human Resources Development Skills			
1. lead colleagues by inspiring them, motivating them, etc.	4.49	.448	Very Great Extent
2. effect continual development and further professional training through continued education and seminars.	4.48	.467	Very Great Extent
3. spearhead team building and development.	4.48	.480	Very Great Extent
4. support staff development in accordance with utilization of their potential for the purpose of the school and its goal's efficient achievements.	4.44	.471	Very Great Extent
5. see to it that all members of the organization are aware what the goals of the organization are.	4.46	.433	Very Great Extent
6. learn to trust people and work with them.	4.36	.617	Very Great Extent
7. learn to give and take feedback.	4.42	.480	Very Great Extent
8. give them and connection with your people.	4.45	.439	Very Great Extent
9. accept and celebrate differences.	4.39	.406	Very Great Extent
10. listen effectively what others think or feel before responding.	3.86	.743	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.38	.354	Very Great Extent
Management Sphere on Teaching Process Administration Sphere			
1. use effective strategies to facilitate positive change on learners' poor habits.	4.45	.452	Very Great Extent
2. plan, act, and evaluate teachers and colleagues to reform the school system that leads to school improvement.	4.43	.536	Very Great Extent
3. consider one's capability to improve himself in his performance by attending trainings and seminars.	4.44	.543	Very Great Extent
4. use potentials to become a leader and to become innovative and to conduct research.	4.45	.538	Very Great Extent
5. value veteran teachers highly to influence and work collaboratively with the teaching practices of the less experience.	4.42	.492	Very Great Extent

6.	apply diverse methods of teaching adaptable to the learner’s ability, learning styles, personality characteristics, and cultural backgrounds.	4.45	.452	Very Great Extent
7.	organize teaching-learning around problem-solving, critical thinking and dealing with issues arising from real life conditions.	4.40	.496	Very Great Extent
8.	seek ways to meet the demands on learners’ acquisition of specific knowledge for productive future functioning.	4.42	.480	Very Great Extent
9.	possess teachable attitude when corrected by considered authorities in the field.	4.50	.413	Very Great Extent
10.	create innovative materials to facilitate teaching-learning activities for quick understanding of learners.	4.42	.505	Very Great Extent
Mean		4.44	.357	Very Great Extent
When Taken as a Whole		4.42	0.35	Very Great Extent

Table 11 presents the outcomes of PhD-EM graduates in communication capabilities—written, oral, and kinesthetic—with an overall mean of 4.36 (SD = 0.36), indicating a very great extent. Written and oral communication both scored 4.36, while kinesthetic communication slightly trailed at 4.35.

In written communication, the highest-rated skill was using soft skills such as empathy and emotional intelligence (M = 4.44), while the lowest was maintaining professionalism despite conflict (M = 4.29). For oral communication, polite language ranked highest (M = 4.43), and showing speech command and humor scored lowest (M = 4.26). In kinesthetic communication, respecting cultural gestures rated highest (M = 4.44), while appropriate use of hand gestures was lowest (M = 4.25).

These findings indicate that PhD-EM graduates communicate clearly, professionally, and with cultural sensitivity—using appropriate verbal, written, and non-verbal strategies. They write directives clearly, communicate with sincerity, and use body language effectively to build trust.

This aligns with Tango-an (2016), who emphasized the importance of strong communication for teachers, and with Khan & Khan (2017), who linked oral communication to student and professional success. Brink (2020) further noted the lasting impact of well-crafted writing.

Strong communication is critical to organizational effectiveness, and PhD-EM graduates, as future school leaders, must align institutional programs with the school’s vision, mission, and goals through clear, strategic communication.

Table 11. Extent of Outcomes Among PhD Educational Management Graduates in Terms of Communication Capabilities

Parameters	Mean	Std. Dev.	Description
Communication Capabilities on Written Communication			
1. follow a definite structure in formal or informal written messages (grammar, unity, and coherence, other mechanics in writing).	4.36	.494	Very Great Extent
2. observe professional choice of words; hides scorn despite of personal conflicts.	4.29	.575	Very Great Extent
3. employ words that are understandable to the readers.	4.37	.541	Very Great Extent
4. write letters with clear directives of free from confusions.	4.42	.583	Very Great Extent
5. observe that letter or memo contents follow the logical order (introduction, body, closing sentences).	4.32	.592	Very Great Extent
6. see that written communication helps define goals, identify problems, and arrive at solutions.	4.32	.582	Very Great Extent
7. show that letter content promotes uniformity of policy, procedure, and builds up proper guidelines for the organization.	4.37	.574	Very Great Extent
8. employ soft skills in written message as the backbone of the organization e.g. interpersonal skill, or emotional intelligence, or empathy and goodwill.	4.44	.489	Very Great Extent
9. keep posters and bulletin boards for reminders and information.	4.36	.472	Very Great Extent
10. respect the communication floe or chain in the organization.	4.37	.456	Very Great Extent
Mean	4.36	.385	Very Great Extent
Communication Capabilities on Oral Communication			
1. speak English fluently and spontaneously.	4.31	.551	Very Great Extent
2. talk clearly and audibly.	4.36	.521	Very Great Extent
3. manifest refinement in spoken language.	4.30	.584	Very Great Extent
4. integrate vocal energy to convey message with a sense of excitement.	4.30	.541	Very Great Extent
5. speak with sincerity.	4.42	.551	Very Great Extent

6.	speaking confidently with calmness and self-control even in the midst of conflict.	4.38	.515	Very Great Extent
7.	use polite words to communicate all the time.	4.43	.449	Very Great Extent
8.	show firmness without being sarcastic in making comments/decisions.	4.42	.528	Very Great Extent
9.	make decisions and policies effectively.	4.41	.508	Very Great Extent
10.	demonstrate command of speech and sense of humor.	4.26	.576	Very Great Extent
	Mean	4.36	.384	Very Great Extent
Communication Capabilities on Kinesthetics Communication				
1.	convey eye language not offensive to others.	4.33	.477	Very Great Extent
2.	use facial expressions to reinforce effective delivery of communication.	4.38	.478	Very Great Extent
3.	observe cultural differences in the use of gesture/culture-specific gestures.	4.44	.471	Very Great Extent
4.	exude self-confidence to acquire trust.	4.39	.524	Very Great Extent
5.	use appropriate arm and hand gestures to illustrate the message.	4.25	.554	Very Great Extent
6.	talk to person in a direct eye to eye contact.	4.26	.520	Very Great Extent
7.	observe proxemics or personal space.	4.37	.584	Very Great Extent
8.	wear smiles when attending to visitors/clients.	4.38	.561	Very Great Extent
9.	convey respectable image in the manner of dressing.	4.32	.538	Very Great Extent
10.	shows interest and importance to the person sitting across the desk.	4.33	.570	Very Great Extent
	Mean	4.35	.315	Very Great Extent
	When Taken as a Whole	4.36	0.36	Very Great Extent

Significant Difference in the Extent of the Graduates' Outcomes as Assessed by Themselves and their Immediate Heads/Supervisors

As shown in Table 12, there exist a difference which is highly significant with a p value of .003 in the professional development of the PhD-EM graduates as assessed by themselves and their respective immediate heads or supervisors. A significant difference also exists in the research capabilities of the PhD-EM graduates with a p value of .036.

Data results show that pursuing a PhD-EM can greatly enhance professional development and build robust research capabilities, which are critical in educational institutions.

As it conforms to that of Andrews (2021), when he underscored that acquiring a PhD could lead to an advanced research skill as it intensely focuses on research, equipping individuals with advanced methodologies for conducting and analyzing studies. PhD-EM graduates may gain skills in designing research projects, collecting and interpreting data, and solving complex, novel problems.

Table 12. Differences on the Extent of Graduates' Outcomes in all Areas as Assessed by PhD-EM Graduates and by their Immediate Heads/Supervisors

Areas	Group	Mean	SD	T	DF	P	Interpretation
Professional Development	PhD-EM Graduates	4.40	.556	3.12	82	.003	Highly Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	3.95	.758				
Research Capabilities	PhD-EM Graduates	4.40	.614	2.14	82	.036	Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.05	.865				
Innovativeness	PhD-EM Graduates	4.39	.653	1.05	82	.294	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.24	.729				
Leadership Capabilities on Behavior	PhD-EM Graduates	4.26	.584	.273	82	.785	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.30	.688				
Leadership Capabilities on Management	PhD-EM Graduates	4.45	.542	.849	82	.398	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.33	.706				
Management Sphere on Strategy Creation	PhD-EM Graduates	4.53	.567	1.48	82	.143	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.34	.597				

Management Sphere on Managing Human Resources Development Skill	PhD-EM Graduates	4.39	.488	.143	82	.887	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.38	.578				
Management Sphere on Teaching Process Administration	PhD-EM Graduates	4.47	.466				Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.40	.616	.559	82	.578	
Communication Capabilities on Written Communication	PhD-EM Graduates	4.45	.460	1.23	82	.205	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.27	.750				
Communication Capabilities on Oral Communication	PhD-EM Graduates	4.43	.537	1.19	82	.238	Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.28	.600				
Communication Capabilities on Kinesthetics Communication	PhD-EM Graduates	4.35	.478				Not Significant
	Immediate Heads/Supervisors	4.34	.572	.062	82	.951	

Even Willyard (n.d.) highlights that programs such as PhDs could prepare individuals for lifelong learning by teaching them to stay updated on the latest research and technological advances. This habit of continuous learning is critical in fields that evolve quickly, enabling them to remain at the forefront of their professions, adapt to changes, and bring cutting-edge knowledge to their organizations.

Willyard (n.d.) added that it could enhance their problem-solving abilities. That is because the depth and complexity of research required for a PhD require high levels of critical thinking and creativity. This experience in tackling intricate issues makes PhD holders effective problem-solvers, able to approach challenges with analytical precision and devise innovative solutions. These problem-solving skills contribute significantly to professional growth in areas that demand adaptive and forward-thinking strategies.

Thus, every successful person has been learning and working at their skills for a long time by taking advantage of any professional development opportunities over the entirety of their career such as those who are PhD-EM graduates. That is because the professional world is becoming increasingly competitive and is constantly changing, so professional development and continual learning is more important than ever in being successful and achieving career goals.

Conclusion

Results showed that outcomes in professional development were rated to a great extent, while research quality and innovativeness were rated to a very great extent. Leadership capabilities, including leadership behavior and management, also showed a very great extent. Similarly, outcomes in management spheres—strategy creation, human resources development, and teaching process administration—were rated to a very great extent. Communication capabilities and their sub-areas (written, oral, and kinesthetic) also showed very great extent. The study's fourth objective was to determine if significant differences existed between self-assessments and supervisor assessments of these outcomes. A significant difference was found only in research capabilities. No significant differences were observed in innovativeness, leadership capabilities (and its sub-areas), management spheres (and its sub-areas), or communication capabilities (and its sub-areas).

Recommendation

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) should continue fostering an equitable and sustainable higher education system that produces innovative, globally competitive, and locally responsive doctoral graduates. These graduates must possess advanced competencies to support sustainable development.

Educational institutions should enhance the PhD-EM program by designing development plans that clarify desired outcomes and define the advanced skills, knowledge, and values students must gain. Programs should be

personalized, promote student interaction, support self-directed learning, and address individual student needs through regular monitoring and feedback.

Graduate school deans should ensure the creation of effective policies for monitoring, evaluation, and feedback aligned with CHED guidelines, focusing on learner-centered education. Institutions must strengthen research efforts to inform curriculum improvement, ensuring the program enhances teacher effectiveness and student competency.

Faculty should assess and improve instructional strategies, collaborate across departments, and develop engaging, student-centered learning activities. Strengthening ties with stakeholders and communities is also vital to achieving quality education.

PhD-EM graduates are encouraged to reflect on their goals and apply their skills and knowledge meaningfully in their fields. Future research could explore doctoral graduates' workplace performance and identify factors influencing successful scholarship programs.

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